

From Siloed to Reusable: The Opening of Digital Collections at Johns Hopkins University

Kathryn (Katie) Gucer, Manager of Digital Collections as Data
Michelle Janowiecki, Digital Content Metadata Specialist

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Introduction

From JScholarship
jscholarship.library.jhu.edu

To

Hopkins Digital Library
digital.library.jhu.edu

- Migration Project: DSpace 6
⇒ Islandora 8
- FAIR: Reuse & Interoperability
 - I Modelling Reusable Metadata
 - II Interoperability w/ Geoportal
 - III Creating Community w/ Batch Ingest

I

Modelling reusable metadata

- "Flat" data to linked data
- Representing entities as graphs not strings
- Improves consistency, findability, and collocation

Comparison of metadata in JScholarship and HDL

Representation of a subject field in JScholarship

```
{"key": "dc.subject.other",  
  "value": "Bronk, Detlev W. (Detlev Wulf),  
1897-1975"}
```

Representation of a subject field in HDL

```
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/subject": [{"@id":  
"https://digital.library.jhu.edu/taxonomy/term/936"}]
```

↓ *Links to*

```
{"@graph": [{"@id":  
"http://digital.library.jhu.edu/taxonomy/term/936", "@type": ["http://schema.org/Person"],  
"http://schema.org/name": [{"@value": "Bronk,  
Detlev W. (Detlev Wulf), 1897-1975",  
"@language": "en"}],  
"http://schema.org/dateModified": [{"@value":  
"2021-10-08T20:35:33+00:00", "@type":  
"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime"}]  
}, {"@id": "http://viaf.org/viaf/23863944"}, {"@id":  
"http://id.loc.gov/authorities/names/n96053230"}]]}]}
```

Taxonomies in HDL

Access Rights	Terms identifying if the access to a resource is public or restricted.
Copyright and Use	Terms using RightsStatements.org to "communicate the copyright and re-use status of digital objects to the public."
Corporate Body	Terms identifying an organization or group of persons that is identified by a particular name and that acts, or may act, as a unit.
Family	Terms identifying multiple persons related by birth, marriage, adoption, civil union, similar legal status, or who present themselves as a family.
Genre/Form	Terms describing a format or artistic category of a resource, not the subject of its contents.
Geographic Location	Terms identifying the name(s) of a place or geographic location by which it is known.
Language	Terms identifying a system of written, spoken, or signed communication in a resource.
Person	Terms identifying an individual or an identity established by an individual, either alone or in collaboration with one or more other individuals.
Resource Type	Terms that broadly characterize(s) the content of the resource, regardless of its original or digital manifestation.
Subject	Terms that indicate a key topic of a resource (what the resource is about).

Entity-Relationships

- Modelled linked data after entity-relationships in catalogue and ArchivesSpace

Equivalent entities across Hopkins Sheridan Libraries

HDL entities	ArchivesSpace entities	Catalogue entities
Access Rights	<i>Local access restriction type</i>	<i>none</i>
Copyright and Use	Rights Statement	<i>none</i>
Corporate Body	Agent: Corporate Entity	Authority record: Corporate names, Meeting names
Family	Agent: Family	Authority record: Personal names (type: Family name)
Genre/Form	Subject: Genre/Form	Authority record: Genre/form terms
Geographic Location	Subject: Geographic	Authority record: Geographic names
Language	Language and Script	<i>MARC List for Languages</i>
Person	Agent: Person	Authority record: Personal names
Resource Type	<i>none</i>	<i>Content Types Scheme</i>
Subject	Subject: Topical	Authority record: Topical terms
Repository Item	Archival Object, Digital Object	Bibliographic record
Collection	Resource	Bibliographic record

Metadata elements & FAIR vocabularies

- Selection of metadata elements from popular namespaces
- Selection of FAIR controlled vocabularies

— — —

Metadata elements

- Dublin Core terms
- Schema.org
- Portland Common Data Model
- MARC Code List for Relators Scheme
- Standard Identifier Schemes

Controlled vocabularies

- Faceted Application of Subject Terminology (FAST)
- Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)
- Library of Congress Name Authority File (LCNAF)
- Virtual International Authority File (VIAF)
- Union List of Artist Names (ULAN)
- ORCID
- Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)
- Library of Congress Genre/Form Terms (LCGFT)
- Geonames.org
- MARC Languages
- DCMI Type Vocabulary
- RightsStatements.org

II Interoperability w/ Geoportal

- Using [International Image Interoperability Framework](#) (IIIF) manifests to share images with GeoBlacklight

About this item

CURRENT ITEM

p006Sheet3N-2E

Description:

Link:

<https://test.digital.library.jhu.edu/node/13382>

RESOURCE

IIIF Manifest

RELATED

Links

IIIF manifest

<http://test.digital.library.jhu.edu/node/13145/manifest>

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III

Reuse & Batch Ingest

Building Community through
Reuse

- Build a robust and diverse community of re/-users
- Batch Ingest
 - External External
 - Internal Community

Reuse & Batch Ingest

External Community
Development

Islandora 8

Open-Source DAMS

Grounded in Reuse

Drupal

Reuse & Batch Ingest

Internal Community
Development

Broaden access to batch ingest among
library staff

Before:

- 2 Staff
- Python scripts
- API
- Bottleneck

User-friendly GUI for librarians to create and update their collections.

Librarians create and update collections using spreadsheets in CSV

After:

- Multiple Staff
- No Python Scripts
- No API
- Gateway

Workbench

Manage

Shortcuts

kgucer1@johnshopkins.edu

Content

Structure

Configuration

People

Reports

Help

[Sheridan Libraries](#)

[Welch Medical Library](#)

[SAIS Library](#)

[Friedheim Music Library](#)

[APL Library](#)

JOHNS HOPKINS
SHERIDAN LIBRARIES

Home

Migrations

Entity: Contact Email (configuration entity) (supports csv) ▼

Upload the source file

Choose File No file chosen

Update existing records

Migrate

Reuse & Batch Ingest

Example:
Community-Generated
Taxonomies

- Ingest service enables library staff to iterate and build on one another's work
- Collective workflow for librarians to create common reservoir of taxonomy terms

Jane Seymour vs Jane Seymour

- Bottleneck => Gateway

Person

Home » Administration » Structure » Taxonomy

+ Add term

You can reorganize the terms in *Person* using their drag-and-drop handles, and group terms under a parent term by sliding them under and to the right of the parent.

NAME	OPERATIONS
✚ Seidell, Atherton	Edit ▾
✚ Seipt, David P.	Edit ▾
✚ Seliger, Howard H. (Howard Harold), 1924-	Edit ▾
✚ Senter, Cheryl	Edit ▾
✚ Sexton, Anne, 1928-1974	Edit ▾
✚ Seyler, Allison	Edit ▾
✚ Shaffer, G. Wilson (George Wilson), 1901-1992	Edit ▾
✚ Shakespeare, William, 1564-1616	Edit ▾
✚ Shapiro, H.A. (Harvey Alan), 1949-	Edit ▾
✚ Shapiro, Karl, 1913-2000	Edit ▾

THE
END

Thank you!

